

Comparative Relationship between Emotional Stability and Academic Performance among Undergraduate Students in Federal Tertiary Institutions in Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

In the midst of a climate of insecurity, this study x-rays the relationship between academic performance and emotional stability among undergraduate students in federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State, Nigeria. This study was carried out using a correlation research design. The population of the study comprised all undergraduate students of the three federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State. 384 students were purposively sampled from the three schools. Emotional Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ) was adopted and adapted for this study and students' CGPAs were used to measure academic performance. *Validity and reliability of ERQ were established showing high internal consistency at 0.81.* Findings indicated that there is a positive relationship between emotional stability and academic performance ($r = 0.7035$). In conclusion, emotional stability has positive relationship with academic performance and can be a tool or aid intervention at enhancing emotional stability to contribute positively to academic performance, particularly in the context of insecurity while taking into consideration gender differences. The study recommended targeted support systems that recognize and address gender differences can be instrumental in fostering a more resilient student population.

Keywords: Academic Performance, Emotional Stability, Gender

Introduction

Security issues has been a recurring theme in Nigeria in past few years, particularly in the northern part of the country, where various terrorist groups, bandits and kidnapers' actions have created a high security concern (Attahiru & Aliyu, 2020). The relatively peaceful northwest part of Nigeria has suddenly turned into a hot zone, where people are afraid to travel, families reporting deaths, and many villages abandoned. The wave of attacks on institutions of learning, particularly in Northern Nigeria, has affected the administration and delivery of educational goals at all levels. The Government and other stakeholders in the education sector have recently found themselves in a quandary on how to find solutions to incessant killings, kidnappings, abductions, destruction of schools and infrastructure by criminal gangs and bandits (Ifedi & Agu, 2021). Even though the efforts by federal and state governments to curb the high level of insecurity in the country have increased, there are still scattered reports of loss of lives and property to the mindless activities of these criminals.

Zamfara state became popular in the news over the last three years due to the increase in insecurity challenges and actions taken by the government to mitigate the situation (Eyinnaya & Olomjobi, 2022). There were series of reported disruptions to academic activities, after some schools were attacked where students and tutors got kidnapped or killed. For instance, on 26th February 2021 bandits were reported to have abducted over three hundred (300) students of Government Girls Junior Secondary School, Jangebe in Talata-Mafara Local Government Area in Zamfara (BBC, 2021), and in the early hours of 1st September, 2021 seventy students were kidnapped at the Government Secondary School Kaya (Premium Times, 2021). The Zamfara state government gave an order on closure of schools in the state on September 1st, 2021 to assess the situation and take actions to rescue the situation (Premium Times, 2021).

The word insecurity has varieties of inferences, crosscutting and multi-dimensional concept which has been subject to debates (Obi, 2015), but generally it denotes danger, hazard, uncertainty, lack of protection, and lack of safety (Ndubuisi-Okolo & Anigbuogu, 2019). Obarisiagbon and Akintoye (2019) insecurity generally refers to the absence of resistance to or protection from harm, peaceful co-existence and development at large. Obi (2015) defined insecurity as a chronic threat to human life, territories, states, religious beliefs, properties and institutions, among others. Extent literature (e.g., Ezemenaka, 2021; Otolurin, 2017; Onime, 2018; Oloyede & Ogunfolaji, 2021; Orhero, 2020; Eneji & Agri, 2020) have discussed different

dimensions of insecurity ranging from food insecurity, health insecurity, environmental insecurity, economic insecurity, political insecurity, human insecurity to personal and community insecurity as outlined in United Nation Developmental Programme (UNDP) Report. However, this study is only limited to two dimensions identified as critical to students' learning namely community and personal insecurity.

Considering the aforementioned, the rise of Boko Haram in 2009, and recent increasing incidence of kidnapping and banditry in Zamfara since 2019 (Eyinnaya & Olomjobi, 2022). There is a need to examine how these occurrences influence student academic performance and emotional stability. Studies (Payne-Sturges et al. 2018; Chamorro-Premuzic & Furnham, 2003) had indicated a discrepancy in the relationship between academic performance and emotional stability. Despite these, there is also a need to examine gender difference in emotional stability, academic performance in light of insecurity in Zamfara state, Nigeria.

According to a study conducted by Payne-Sturges et al. (2018), insecurity can be a major factor in the emotional stability and academic performance of undergraduate students. This study found that feeling insecure in their academic environment can lead to undergraduate students feeling overwhelmed and unable to concentrate, which can have a direct impact on their academic performance. However, Payne-Sturges et al. (2018) was unable to factor in gender lens, hence the need for this study to examine gender difference in academic performance and emotional stability in an insecure setting. Furthermore, insecurity can lead to feelings of social isolation and loneliness, which can have a negative impact on a student's emotional stability. These feelings can lead to a lack of motivation and a decrease in performance, hence necessitating the need to examine gender lens in this regard.

The theory of education productivity was propounded by Walberg et al. (1986), discussed broadly factors that impact students' learning and academic performances. It is an assessment of academic achievement where Walberg used a variation of methods to identify the factors that influence academic performance. Walberg identified nine factors that require optimization to increase student achievement of cognitive and affective outcomes. These are; ability or prior achievement, age, motivation or self-concept as indicated by personality tests or willingness to persevere on learning tasks; the instructional variables of, the quantity of instruction, and quality of the instructional experience; and educationally stimulating psychological aspects of the home environment, the classroom or school environment, the peer group environment, and the mass media (especially television). This study posited that environmental and personal factors i.e., personal and community insecurity can influence students' learning since students are the product of their environment (Ojeleye, Mutiu & Kareem, 2020).

The uncertainty surrounding security of life and property of the people of any State can hinder the growth of sustainable development and educational advancement of such a State. Nwosu et al. (2019) argued that an insecure institution environment affects students adversely; situations of insecurity trigger traumatic disorder and toxic stress that can affect learning negatively. For example, a large number of students of the federal institutions in Zamfara live in Damba village, where there have been some reports of abductions and bandit attacks over the last few months (Premium Times, 2021). DC Payne-Sturges et al. (2018) found that undergraduate students who experienced higher levels of insecurity were more likely to report higher levels of anxiety, depression, and loneliness. Furthermore, these students had lower self-esteem and reported lower academic performance than those who did not experience insecurity.

Consequently, this study aims to explore the impact of insecurity context in the relationship between emotional stability and academic performance of undergraduate students of Federal Institutions Zamfara State. Also, the study will examine the linkage of gender lens between emotional stability and academic performance of this population. Several studies (Hyde, et al., 1990; Feingold, 1994; Duckworth & Seligman, 2006; Graziano, et al. 2007; Ojeleye et al. 2020) indicating how gender difference influences students' performances, hence necessitating the need for examining gender lens with the context of this inquiries.

Universities and colleges across the world are continuously striving to cater to their students to ensure that they develop into successful and well-rounded individuals. However, within this environment, most students are faced with a multitude of pressures and stressors that threaten their academic performance, mental health and general emotional stability yet they are also expected to compete in both local and international labour market, hence this the dilemma. This dilemma also include gap between social class, attainment of Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) among others. Learned helplessness, fear of failure, and fear of academic success can lead to strong feelings of academic insecurity, which hinders students' emotional stability. Moreover, when students feel emotionally insecure, it can hinder their academic performance since students tend to put minimal effort into their school work as a coping mechanism. Therefore, it is important to create a safe, encouraging learning environment that allows students to feel secure, empowered and actively engaged in their education via having insight on how these insecurity influence students. By doing so, we can help them to maintain emotional stability, build positive academic identities, and ultimately, enhance their academic performance.

Objectives of the Study

The specific research objectives of this study are:

1. To examine the relationship between emotional stability and students' academic performance among students in federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State
2. To investigate whether difference exists between academic performance of male and female students in Federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State.
3. To examine whether difference exist in emotional stability of male and female students in Federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State.

Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant relationship between emotional stability and mean academic performance scores among students in Federal tertiary institution in Zamfara State.
2. There is no significant difference in mean academic performance scores of male and female students in federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State.
3. There is no significant difference in emotional stability of male and female students in federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State.

Methodology

This study was carried out using a correlation research design. The population of the study comprised all undergraduate students of the three federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State, the three schools are: Federal University Gusau (FUG), Gusau, Federal College of Education (Technical), Gusau and The Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda, Zamfara State. Three hundred and eighty-four (384) students were sampled using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) to determine the sample size, purposively sampling was used. One hundred and twenty-eight (128) students were purposively selected in each school and also sixty-four (64) males and sixty-four (64) females were sampled in each institution. Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ) developed by Gross and John (2003) was adopted and adapted for this study and CGPA was used to measure academic performance for this study. Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ) is a 10-item scale designed to measure respondents' tendency to regulate their emotions in two ways: (1) Cognitive Reappraisal and (2) Expressive Suppression. This instrument uses a 7-point Likert-type scale but was adapted to 5-point Likert scale for the purpose of this study. Respondents answer each item on a 5-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to (strongly agree). This was used to measure emotional stability among the respondents. A pilot study was also carried out using undergraduate students from Federal University Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State. Data collected from these undergraduate students were analysed using Gutterman Split-half and 0.81 Cronbach Alpha was obtained for ERQ.

Results

Hypothesis One

There is no significant relationship between emotional stability and mean academic performance scores among students in Federal tertiary institution in Zamfara State.

Table 3: Pearson r results of emotional stability and academic performance of students federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State

Variables	N	r	df	sig.	decision
Emotional stability	384	0.7035	382	0.000	significant
Academic performance					

Table 3 shows that R-value was 0.7035 with p-value of 0.000 calculated at the alpha level of .05. since the calculated p-value of .000 is less than the alpha level of .05, therefore, the null hypothesis that says, there is no significant relationship between emotional stability and academic performance of students of federal tertiary institutions is rejected at .05 level of significance. This shows that there is enough evidence that a significant positive relationship exists between emotional stability and academic performance at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference in mean academic performance scores of male and female students in federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State.

Table 4: t-test showing gender difference in Academic Performance amidst insecurity

Variables	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	p-value
Male Students	192	37.41	49.50	382	2.309	0.0350
Female Students	192	32.95	40.56			

Table 4 shows that t-value was 2.309 with p-value of 0.0350 calculated at the significance level of 0.05. Since the calculated p-value of 0.0350 is less than the alpha levels, therefore, the null hypothesis which stated there is no significant difference between academic performance of male and female undergraduate students is rejected. This shows that significant difference exists in academic performance of male and female undergraduates' students. It reveals that there is enough evidence that the male students with mean value of 37.41 have higher academic performance than female students with mean value of 32.95 at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis Three

There is no significant difference in emotional stability of male and female students in federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State.

Table 5: t-test showing gender difference in emotional stability amidst insecurity

Variables	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	p-value
Male Students	192	39.64	38.65	382	2.41	0.005
Female Students	192	35.54	32.90			

Table 5 shows that t-value was 2.41 with p-value of 0.005 calculated at the significance level of 0.05. Since the calculated p-value of 0.005 is less than the alpha levels, therefore, the null hypothesis which stated there is no significant difference between emotional stability of male and female undergraduate students is rejected. This shows that significant difference exists in emotional stability of male and female undergraduates' students. It reveals that there is enough evidence that the male students with mean value of 39.64 have higher emotional than female students with mean value of 35.54 at 0.05 level of significance.

Discussion of Findings

The study explored the relationship between emotional stability and academic performance in an environment with increasing insecurity among federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State. The findings are discussed in the following heading: emotional stability and academic performance in the context of insecurity and gender differences in emotional stability and academic performance in the context of insecurity. The findings of the study reveal several interesting patterns in the emotional stability, academic performance, and gender differences among undergraduate students in federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State, particularly in the context of insecurity. These findings provide valuable insights that contribute to our understanding of the psychological and academic aspects of students facing security challenges.

Emotional Stability in the Context of Security challenges

Descriptively, emotional stability has two domain which are cognitive appraisal and expressive suppression. The result indicated that majority of undergraduate students (63%) experienced high changes in their thinking and appraisal of situations, indicating a significant level of cognitive appraisal. Likewise, 65% of the respondents was able emotional expression were highly suppressed. This also suggests that students are actively engaging with and processing the challenges posed by insecurity. This high cognitive appraisal and expressive suppression could be attributed to the unique socio-political context of Zamfara State, emphasizing the need for educational institutions to incorporate coping mechanisms within their academic programs. This was similar to Payne-Sturges et al. (2018) notion that undergraduate students feeling insecure in an academic institution can be overwhelming, leading to a direct impact on academic performance, hence the need for examining the connection between academic performance.

Emotional Stability and Academic Performance

The findings revealed a positive relationship between emotional stability and academic performance in the context of insecurity. This implies that the more student's emotional stability is increasing positive so will academic performance. This also implies that students who exhibit higher emotional stability are more likely to achieve better academic outcomes. This finding underscores the importance of integrating emotional intelligence and resilience-building programs into the academic curriculum. Educational institutions should consider implementing initiatives that promote emotional well-being to enhance overall student success, especially in regions facing security challenges.

This further inform that in addressing insecurity negative impact on students' performance, therapy centered around improving emotional stability would have an indirect effect on academic performance. Chamorro-Premuzic & Furnham, (2003) indicated that some emotional trait could impair academic performance likewise, Graziano, et al., and Xu, et al., (2020) also indicated that ability to regulate emotion reflect academic success or performance. This further buttress the current study finding that emotion have a positive relationship with academic performance.

Gender Differences in Emotional Stability and Academic performance

The study highlights noticeable gender differences in emotional stability among students in the face of insecurity. Male students demonstrated higher emotional stability, both in terms of cognitive reappraisal and expressive suppression, compared to their female counterparts. These gender variations may be linked to societal expectations, coping mechanisms, or individual resilience. Understanding these differences is crucial for implementing targeted support systems and interventions to enhance emotional well-being, particularly for female students. More so, the study also highlighted gender difference in academic performance in the context of insecurity. Likewise, same trend was observed as illustrated above Male students demonstrated higher academic performance than their female counterpart. This further buttress that the positive relationship between emotional stability and academic performance.

The gender differences in emotional stability and academic performance amid insecurity underscore the need for tailored interventions. Understanding these distinctions allows for the development of targeted support programs that address the specific challenges faced by male and female students. Strategies to enhance emotional stability and academic performance should be gender-sensitive, recognizing and accommodating the unique needs and responses of each gender group.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study sheds light on the intricate relationship between emotional stability, academic performance, and gender differences among undergraduate students in federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State, particularly in the context of insecurity. The results show how important emotional health is for academic performance and how different genders handle the difficulties that come with insecurity in different ways. A high degree of cognitive evaluation was demonstrated by most students, suggesting that they actively engaged with the complicated insecure environment. Male students demonstrated higher emotional stability compared to their female counterparts, revealing potential gender-specific responses to insecurity. Additionally, the study revealed a substantial positive relationship between emotional stability and academic performance, emphasizing the crucial role of psychological resilience in achieving positive learning outcomes. One area of focus was students' academic performance in the context of insecurity; a significant number of them had moderate performance. The small percentage of kids who perform exceptionally well academically highlights the necessity of focused interventions to lessen the influence of security issues on learning objectives.

The study emphasizes the need of putting in place customized support systems inside educational institutions from a practical standpoint. Counseling services, stress management programs, and gender-sensitive initiatives can contribute to enhancing emotional stability and, subsequently, academic success. These practical implications align with the broader goal of promoting a resilient and thriving student community in the midst of challenging circumstances. The theoretical implications of this study resonate with the theory of education productivity, emphasizing the critical role of emotional stability in optimizing cognitive functioning and, consequently, academic productivity. By acknowledging the interconnectedness of emotional well-being and academic success, educational institutions can incorporate emotional intelligence principles into their frameworks, creating an environment conducive to effective learning. In summary, this study contributes valuable insights to the understanding of how emotional stability, gender dynamics, and academic performance intersect in the context of insecurity. The implications call for proactive measures to address emotional well-being and foster an inclusive educational environment that supports the diverse needs of students, ultimately enhancing their overall learning experience and success.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations emerge to address the identified issues related to emotional stability, gender differences, and academic performance in the context of insecurity among undergraduate students in federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State:

1. Firstly, implementation of emotional well-being programmes. Universities of higher learning must make the launch of comprehensive programs for emotional well-being a top priority. These programs ought to include stress management classes, counseling services, and resilience-building exercises designed to provide kids the tools they need to deal with the difficulties that come with uncertainty.
2. Second, there is a need for gender-sensitive support systems. Institutions must to provide support systems that are considerate of the distinct requirements of both male and female students, taking into account the gender disparities in emotional stability. A more welcoming and encouraging atmosphere might also be promoted by interventions that are specifically designed to address the issues that each gender faces.
3. Thirdly, emotional intelligence needs to be incorporated into tertiary curricula. Incorporating this in educational curricula like in courses or workshops on emotional intelligence can contribute to the overall development of students, helping them cultivate skills necessary for emotional stability which would aid academic performance.

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